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inicial del cloud continuo de
6GSMART
v1.0

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4 List of Acronyms

API	Application Programming Interfaces
AWS	Amazon web Services
BGP	Border Gateway Protocol
CaaS	Container as a Service
CEI	Cloud-edge-IoT
CPU	Central processing unit
CSC	Communication Service Customer
CSC	Communication Service Customer
CSP	Communication Service Provider
CSPs	Communications service providers
ECN	Edge Compute Network
ECOMP	Enhanced Control, Orchestration, Management, and Policy
ECS	Amazon Elastic Container Service
EKS	Kubernetes Service
ETSI	European Telecommunications Standards Institute
GDC	Google Distributed Cloud
GPU	Graphics processing unit
IIoT	Industrial IoT
IoT	The Internet of Things
K8s	Kubernetes
LXC	Linux kernel containers
MEC	Multi-access Edge Computing
MEC	Multi-access Edge Computing
NF	Network functions
NFV	Network functions virtualization
NOP	Network Operator
NOP	Network operator
OGC	Ori Global Cloud
ONAP	Open Network Automation Platform
OSG	Open-Source Group
OSM	Open-Source Mano
RAN	Radio access network
RIC	RAN Intelligent Controller
SDK	software development kit
SDN	Software-Defined Networking
SEP	Service Enablement Platform
VAN	Virtual Application Network
VMs	Virtual Machine
VNS	Virtual network services
VPN	Virtual Private Network

5 Executive Summary

Numerous efforts are being made in the telecommunications and cloud ecosystems to respond to the challenges of continuum cloud computing. Both public cloud providers and orchestration solution providers for telecommunications operators are making significant efforts to respond to the deployment of applications at the edge. At this moment we find ourselves in a very fragmented landscape with open-source solutions (OSM, ONAP), public cloud solutions (AWS, GDC, Azure), private IT NFV providers (VMware, RedHat, Netcraker, NearByOne) and solutions from traditional vendors (Nokia, Ericsson).

Current solutions do not provide an adequate response to the new challenges of continuous cloud such as partition tolerance in distributed applications, lack of automated mesh network/communication features, volatile resource management, telco cloud solutions not replicable in on-prem environments.

At 6GSMART-ICC we are going to study some of the above challenges to identify the reference designs that should be followed in the development of the continuous cloud orchestrator. Specifically, we are going to work on:

- Modeling and management of volatile resources. It is about minimizing the unavailability time of a given application component due to the characteristics of volatile resources.
- Deployment model based on intent. The orchestrator maintains full control over the clouds that should be used to deploy the application components.
- Virtual application networks that make distributed application programming a reality. Through these networks, various autoscaling mechanisms will be studied.

6 Introduction

This document analyzes and reviews the state of the art of continuous cloud and meta-OS technologies currently under development in the telecommunications and cloud computing ecosystems, including projects beyond 5G and 6G. The main design principles and existing software projects to be used as a reference in the design of the continuous industrial cloud orchestration system of 6GSMART are also identified.

The document is organized in five main chapters:

- Chapter 5: Executive summary.
- Chapter 7: Includes a review on Industry 4.0 ecosystem, serverless computing and resource orchestration solutions.
- Chapter 8: Includes technical innovations on:
 - IoT-edge-cloud continuum in multi-domain environments
 - Intent mechanisms to integrate OT workloads into telco environments.
- Chapter 9: Includes system requirements and high-level system design.
- Chapter 10: Summary and conclusions.

7 Cloud continuum orchestration in manufacturing environments

7.1 Issue #1: Industry 4.0 ecosystem

Currently, the manufacturing sector is undergoing a fundamental transformation known as the "industry 4.0"¹. Industry 4.0 describes the "fourth industrial revolution", which aims at transforming today's factories into intelligently connected production information systems that operate well beyond the physical boundaries of the factory premises. The main goals of Industry 4.0 are to enhance worker support, flexibility, adaptability, resource efficiency, cost efficiency, worker support, and the standard of industrial production and logistics. Factories of the future leverage the smart integration of "cyber-physical-systems" and Internet of Things (IoT) solutions in industrial processes².

This digitalization and automation of the manufacturing sector is driven by four disruptions: (i) the astonishing rise in data volumes, computational power, and connectivity; (ii) the emergence of analytics and business-intelligence capabilities; (iii) new forms of human-machine interaction such as tactic interfaces and augmented-reality systems; (iv)

¹ X M. Wollschlaeger, T. Sauter, and J. Jasperneite, "The Future of Industrial Communication: Automation Networks in the Era of IoT and Industry 4.0", IEEE Industrial Electronics Magazine, pp. 17-27, 2017.

² S. K. Rao and R. Prasad, "Impact of 5G Technologies on Industry 4.0", Wireless Personal Communications, vol. 100, no. 1, pp. 1-15, 2018.

improvements in transferring digital instructions to the physical world, such as advanced robotics and 3D printing.

There are a number of analyst reports that proves the market growth and business opportunities unleashed by industry 4.0 for this decade. Examples of publicly available figures reported by some analyst companies are listed below:

- **Fortune Business Insights**³ projects a market size to USD 377.30 billion by 2029 from 114.55 billion in 2021, exhibiting a CAGR of 16.3% during the 2022-2029 period.
- **Market & Markets projects**⁴ a market size to 165.5 billion USD by 2026 from 73.9 billion USD at a CAGR of 20.6%
- **Allied Market Research**⁵ projects a market size to USD 618.4 billion by 2031 from 113.4 billion in 2021, growing at a CAGR of 18.8% during the 2022-2031 period.

Table 1 glues the main takeaways resulting from the top-tier analyst reports on industry 4.0. Apart from the ones noted earlier, these include Gartner, STL and McKinsey.

Table 1: Industry 4.0 market segment – main insights

Topic	Summary
Market segmentation	<ul style="list-style-type: none"> • Component: Solutions, Services. • Technology: AI, 3D printing, AR/VR systems, IoT, cyber-security, advanced robotics and big data. • Enterprise size: Small & Medium Enterprises, Large Enterprises. • Industry: Automotive, Manufacturing, Energy & Utilities, Electronics & Consumer Goods, Oil & Gas, Aerospace & Defense.
Market challenges	<ul style="list-style-type: none"> • Skills gap • Data privacy and security • High implementation costs • Legacy systems • Fragmented standardization landscape • Regulatory challenges
Market Opportunities	<ul style="list-style-type: none"> • Increased efficiency • Improved product quality • Predictive maintenance • Customization • Enhanced supply chain management • New business models
Market recommendation	<ul style="list-style-type: none"> • Embrace digital transformation • Focus on upskilling and reskilling employees • Develop a comprehensive Industry 4.0 strategy⁶.

³ <https://www.fortunebusinessinsights.com/industry-4-0-market-102375>

⁴ https://www.marketsandmarkets.com/Market-Reports/industry-4-market-102536746.html?gclid=CjwKCAjw44mlBhAQEiwAqP3eVpvXTOFto2IX3fFaD1yH4m4C87_20LdQTCJsNEj6XaaavugEFQJ5XxoCfuoQAvD_BwE

⁵ <https://www.alliedmarketresearch.com/industry-4-0-market>

⁶ Siemens white paper, “Practical Pathways to Industry 4.0”. Link

	<ul style="list-style-type: none"> • Partner with technology providers • Explore new business models
Market Regional Analysis	<ul style="list-style-type: none"> • North America: it is one of the largest markets for Industry 4.0, with the United States leading the way. The region has a strong focus on innovation and technological advancements, and many large corporations are investing in Industry 4.0 technologies to gain a competitive advantage. • Europe: it is also a significant market for Industry 4.0, with Germany being the leading country in the region. The region has a well-established manufacturing sector, and there is a growing emphasis on digitalization to drive growth and efficiency. • Asia-Pacific: this region is rapidly adopting Industry 4.0 technologies, with China, Japan, and South Korea leading the way. The region has a large manufacturing base, and many companies are investing in digitalization to improve their operations and stay competitive. • Middle East & Asia: the region is also experiencing growth in the Industry 4.0 market, with countries such as the United Arab Emirates and Saudi Arabia leading the way. The region has a focus on developing new industries, and Industry 4.0 technologies are seen as key to achieving this goal. • Latin America: it is a smaller market for industry 4.0, but there is a growing interest in the region. Brazil and Mexico are the market champions.

7.2 Issue #2: Serverless computing

According to Wikipedia: *“Serverless computing is a cloud computing execution model in which the cloud provider allocates machine resources on demand, taking care of the servers on behalf of their customers. “Serverless” is a misnomer in the sense that servers are still used by cloud service providers to execute code for developers. However, developers of serverless applications are not concerned with capacity planning, configuration, management, maintenance, fault tolerance, or scaling of containers, VMs, or physical servers. Serverless computing does not hold resources in volatile memory; computing is rather done in short bursts with the results persisted to storage. When an app is not in use, there are no computing resources allocated to the app. Pricing is based on the actual amount of resources consumed by an application.”*

Serverless computing is gaining more acceptance every day due to the lower costs it entails for companies and the offer of this type of services by the large public cloud providers: Amazon (**AWS lambda**), Google (**Google Functions**) and Microsoft (**Azure Functions**).

Each public provider offers different APIs to execute the business logic (also called FaaS, Function as a Service) and offers different storage services, security tokens, user identification, etc., which allow completing the needs that the applications may require. For example, a typical application deployed with the serverless computing model on AWS has the following architecture as depicted in Figure 1:

Source AWS

Figure 1 Serverless application on AWS

In this case, the application consists of a web server, business logic (Lambda functions), security token service (STS), user authentication (Cognito), and database (Dynamo). As you can see, the application is linked to the use of the different AWS services.

Since each provider offers its own APIs and services to implement the applications, we are faced with the possibility of having a certain vendor lock-in. There are serverless application development platforms that allow the deployment of applications in different public clouds, minimizing that vendor lock-in. Two of the most used frameworks are [pulumi](#)⁷ and [serverless framework](#)⁸.

Pulumi

Pulumi is a framework that follows of model Infrastructure as code, that is an efficient and repeatable way of building a serverless application with programming languages and deploying the website to your preferred cloud.

Pulumi's open source, infrastructure as code SDK that lets you build and deploy static websites with TypeScript/JavaScript, Python, Go, Java, .NET, and YAML. The main benefits include:

Programming Languages: Define infrastructure as code in your favorite language instead of domain-specific languages or clicking through cloud consoles.

Unified Function and Infrastructure Code: Manage cloud function code and infrastructure code together in a single program.

⁷ <https://www.pulumi.com/templates/serverless-application/>

⁸ <https://www.serverless.com/framework/docs>

Fast, Easy Deployment: Quickly deploy your serverless application with a CLI or from a CI/CD workflow.

Rapid Development: Author, version, test, and release infrastructure changes just like software.

Application Templates: Provide application templates for principal cloud providers as shown in Figure 2.

Source www.pulumi.com

Figure 2 Pulumi serverless application templates

Serverless framework

The Serverless Framework pioneered serverless architecture on AWS, a transformative approach to building applications on cloud infrastructure that auto-scales, incurs no charges when idle, and typically demands minimal maintenance. Today, it continues to be the leading developer tool for deploying serverless architectures.

Here are the Serverless Framework's highlights:

Empowering - Build more and manage less with serverless architectures.

Many Use-Cases - Choose from tons of efficient serverless use-cases (APIs, Scheduled Tasks, Event Handlers, Streaming Data Pipelines, Web Sockets & more).

Automated - Deploys both code and infrastructure together, resulting in out-of-the-box serverless apps.

Easy - Enjoy simple syntax to safely deploy AWS Lambda functions, event sources and more without being a cloud expert.

Multi-Language - Supports Node.js, Python, Java, Go, C#, Ruby, Swift, Kotlin, PHP, Scala, & F#

Full Lifecycle - Manages the lifecycle of your serverless architecture (build, deploy, update, monitor, troubleshoot).

Multi-Domains - Group domains into Serverless Services for easy management of code, resources & processes, across large projects & teams.

Multi-Environments - Built-in support for multiple stages (e.g. development, staging, production).

Guardrails - Loaded with automation, optimization and best practices.

Extensible - Extend or modify the Framework and its operations via Plugins.

Plugin Ecosystem - Extend or modify the Framework and its operations via Plugins.

7.3 Issue #3: Resource orchestration solutions

Many of the 5G-specific use cases identified by communications service providers (CSPs) as high-revenue, high-margin services have a dependency on low-latency, high-bandwidth connectivity from the network edge to the end user device. The only way to provide these service characteristics is with a strong 5G Multi-access Edge Computing (MEC) strategy using edge cloud for compute.

Communication service providers are deploying their own private cloud at edge locations using specialized Edge Orchestration solutions. These solutions range from open-source solutions, through solutions from traditional network providers (Nokia, Huawei), to solutions from private IT NFV providers (VMware, RedHat, Netcraker, NearbyOne) and public clouds (AWS, GDC, Azure). Some of the most relevant solutions for the telco edge are:

Open source

OSM

Open-Source MANO (OSM) is an ETSI-hosted initiative, aimed at the deployment of open-source NFV management and orchestration software stacks, and is fully aligned with the ETSI-developed NFV reference architecture. The ETSI entity labeled OSM as OSG (Open-Source Group) – one of the first projects to be given this association – which allows open-source projects to be developed under ETSI.

ONAP

The Open Network Automation Platform (ONAP) is an open-source software platform. It enables the design, creation, and orchestration of services on the infrastructure layer sitting on top of individual virtual network functions or SDN, or a combination of the two. ONAP was originally developed as a combination of OPEN-O (Linux Foundations OPEN-Orchestrator Project), and the AT&T ECOMP (Enhanced Control, Orchestration, Management, and Policy) platforms, forming its own unique code.

Traditional Network Vendors

Nokia

Nokia integrated RAN Intelligent Controller (RIC) and Multi-access Edge Computing (MEC) capabilities are implemented in its Service Enablement Platform (SEP).

Nokia SEP supports innovative RAN use cases and provides unique value by implementing O-RAN standardized near-real-time RIC capabilities together with ETSI-defined MEC Application Programming Interfaces (APIs). The SEP enables the RAN control of the RIC and the service awareness of the MEC to be connected and used efficiently and flexibly to provide valuable use cases. The SEP can be deployed to support one or both of the standards-defined services.

Huawei

Multi-access Edge Computing (MEC) is a network solution that provides services and computing functions required by users on edge nodes. It makes application services and content closer to users and implements network collaboration, providing users with reliable and ultimate service experience. Huawei proposes the next-generation 5G MEC solution – Clover, which means the next-generation MEC solution integrates "connectivity + computing + X", achieving dynamic and intelligent connections, super-performance heterogeneous computing, and innovation (X) anytime, anywhere, accelerating edge service innovation, enabling new 2B business

Private IT NFV Providers

VMware Telco Cloud Automation

Telco Cloud Automation offers consistent multi-cloud operations, from infrastructure to services and slices. It applies a cloud-smart approach to abstract the cloud evolution complexity and delivers optimized network resources on-demand, lowering operating expenses and bolstering revenue-generating services

Red Hat OpenShift

Using Red Hat OpenShift in a cloud-native architecture, one of the most fundamental software abstractions is the notion of MachineSets. When determining the desired number of nodes for a cluster, MachineSets govern the management of machines, which in turn governs the underlying resources (i.e., VMs) available today. In the same way that ReplicaSets maintain a stable set of pods in traditional Kubernetes environments, MachineSets provide a representation of the underlying physical hardware, including the cloud provider, image, and other flavors of the logical node itself.

Netcracker

Netcracker's foray into edge cloud orchestration started from its role in Vodafone's Ocean project where it was selected as Vodafone's distributed orchestration vendor of choice. Since then, Netcracker has won a number of awards for its orchestration capabilities including the 2020 Layer123 Network Transformation Award and the 2021 MEF Award for Market Game Changer. The company scored its latest big win when Etisalat selected Netcracker for domain orchestration for dynamic 5G slicing in 2021. Netcracker's Edge Domain Orchestration is part of its Domain Service Orchestration portfolio. Currently, the company is focused on RAN orchestration at telcos' edges, however, it is planning to add edge application orchestration by incorporating ETSI MEC APIs. This being said, Netcracker's role in the edge ecosystem is largely limited

to edge orchestration for network functions as it focuses on lifecycle management to support service orchestration.

NearbyOne

NearbyOne, Nearby's edge cloud orchestration platform, offers end-to-end, cross-domain orchestration capabilities. The platform has strengths across different workload types and specific capabilities such as edge node discovery and closed-loop automation. Nearby Computing is among the few companies that are able to provide application lifecycle management and interface with the network at the same time. NearbyOne is also unique in its ability to support different types of applications across both on-prem edge (apps, network functions including private cellular and uCPE) and the network edge (apps & network functions e.g., RAN, distributed core.).

On the other hand, the big players in the public cloud are taking all their experience in the public cloud to the edge and on-premises. The three main ones (Microsoft, Amazon and Google) are making important efforts that providers of communication services should not lose sight of. These providers provide complete solutions (on-premise, edge, cloud) both for the deployment of distributed applications and for the deployment of the 5G network itself (slicing or private). The proposals made by these major players are:

Google Distributed Cloud

With Google Distributed Cloud, customers will be able to migrate or modernize applications and process data locally with a set of Google Cloud services like databases, machine learning, data analytics, container management services, and third-party services. Depending on the organization, you can run Google Distributed Cloud products and solutions in one of four location types: Google's network edge, Operator edge, Customer edge, and Customer data center as shown in Figure 3.

Source cloud.google.com

Figure 3 Google Distributed Cloud

This solution includes:

Google Distributed Cloud Edge

Google Distributed Cloud Edge (GDC Edge) is a fully managed product that brings Google Cloud's infrastructure and services closer to where data is being generated and consumed. GDC Edge empowers communication service providers to run 5G Core and radio access network (RAN) functions at the edge. It also enables an ecosystem of partners and developers to create enterprise applications to meet mission-critical use cases such as computer vision and Google AI edge inferencing. GDC Edge is generally available, building on our telecommunication solutions and empowering CSPs to deliver new experiences which leverage 5G and edge.

Google Distributed Cloud Hosted

Google Distributed Cloud Hosted (GDC Hosted) is a fully disconnected cloud designed to run sensitive workloads, supporting customers with strict data residency, security, and privacy requirements. GDC Hosted includes the hardware, software, local control plane, and operational tooling necessary to deploy, operate, scale, and secure a complete managed cloud. Customers in regulated industries, such as government, financial services, healthcare, and manufacturing are empowered to deliver on business priorities and help modernize even their most sensitive or confidential workloads.

Google Distributed Cloud Virtual

Google Distributed Cloud Virtual (GDC Virtual) is a software-only solution that enables you to extend a consistent dev and operational experience to your existing data center environments. Ideal for new and existing enterprise applications, or for real-time analytics that have specific hardware, security, and locality requirements which are most suitable for on-premises data centers. GDC Virtual is enabled by Anthos and allows customers to begin modernizing infrastructure, apps, and data in place - at a pace that makes sense for their business. GDC Virtual is self-managed and deployable onto virtual machines and bare metal systems, supporting greater choice and customization based on your unique needs.

Microsoft Azure Stack

Microsoft Azure Stack extends Azure services and capabilities to any environment, from the data center to edge locations and remote offices. Application providers can build, deploy, and run edge compute and hybrid applications consistently across IT ecosystem, with flexibility for diverse workloads as shown in Figure 4.

Source azure.microsoft.com

Figure 4 Microsoft Azure Stack

This solution includes:

Azure Stack Edge

With azure stack edge the following use cases can be implemented:

Machine learning at the edge

Azure Stack Edge helps you troubleshoot latency or connectivity issues by processing data close to its source. Run machine learning models in edge locations. Transfer the dataset you need, entire or just a subset, to Azure to retrain the model for further improvement.

Internet of Things (IoT)

Process, sort, and analyze your data center or IoT data to instantly understand what you can take action on, what you need to keep and store in the cloud, and what you don't.

Processing capacity at the edge and in remote sites

Run applications in remote locations to speed up transactions and overcome bandwidth constraints. On-premises applications will continue to work even when connectivity to the cloud is limited.

Normative compliance

Make sure the data you send back to the cloud doesn't violate any regulations by using ML models that alert you if potentially sensitive data is detected and you can take action on-premises.

Azure Stack Hub

Azure Stack Hub extends Azure Stack so you can run applications on-premises and offer Azure services in your data center. As organizations rush to digitally transform, many realize they can move faster by using public cloud services to build solutions on modern architectures and update legacy applications.

However, many workloads must remain on-premises, for example, due to technological and regulatory hurdles. Microsoft gives you everything you need with a wide range of hybrid cloud options and cloud innovation for all your workloads, wherever they are.

AWS Solutions for Hybrid and Multicloud

AWS container services make it easier to manage your underlying infrastructure, whether on premises or in the cloud, so you can focus on innovation and your business needs. Deploy and run containerized applications on AWS with Amazon Elastic Kubernetes Service (EKS) and Amazon Elastic Container Service (ECS), or in hybrid environments with Amazon EKS Anywhere and Amazon ECS Anywhere. Build self-managed Kubernetes clusters on AWS, on premises, or on other clouds using Amazon EKS Distro, the same open-source version of Kubernetes used by Amazon EKS. View and explore all of your Kubernetes clusters, applications, and associated cloud resources running in hybrid and multi-cloud environments in the Amazon EKS console using the Amazon EKS Connector.

AWS has different solutions for compute services:

AWS Outposts

AWS Outposts allows you to run AWS infrastructure and services on premises for a consistent hybrid experience.

AWS Wavelength

AWS Wavelength embeds AWS compute and storage services at the edge of 5G networks for a faster application response time.

AWS Local Zones

AWS Local Zones put AWS services near large population and industry centers so you can reach local users in milliseconds.

AWS Snow

AWS Snow devices collect and process data between the edge and AWS so that your apps run in all conditions.

8 Technical innovations

8.1 IoT-edge-cloud continuum in multi-domain environments

8.1.1 State of the art

Continuous orchestration is growing as a solution for the requirements of IoT systems. At the same time, they integrate a large number of devices that generate an immense amount of data with their respective applications, which require real-time processing,

response times, reliability and security.

Edge computing aims to offload the cloud by moving services to the edge of the network, closer to IoT devices. Where cloud continuity refers to a highly distributed environment. With this we have a decentralization and dynamism that extends from the devices to the cloud.

Service orchestration is key to ensure optimal placement of services in this complex environment, both in time and space, according to real-time application requirements, taking into account workload balancing, fault tolerance and system stability.

The architecture of centralizing data in the cloud has proven to be unsustainable, because the overwhelming amount of data leads to network congestion and slows down cloud processing. Besides, many IoT solutions require data processing in near real time.

For these reasons, edge computing that is distributed and decentralized must be developed. Where cloud services move from the cloud to the edge of the network, they run on multiple nodes located between the IoT devices and the cloud. For this reason, a solution must be provided to orchestrate cloud services within this environment.

Horizon Europe's Cluster 4 Destination 3

Several projects funded by the European Union⁹ has been selected recently to provide solutions to all the challenges of the IoT cloud continuum. Figure 5 shows the projects according to the problem they try to solve.

Figure 5 EU meta-os projects

Below is a brief description for each of the projects and coordination actions.

⁹ https://ec.europa.eu/newsroom/repository/document/2022-25/Factsheet__Horizon_Europe_metaOS_projects_8aBnKLIqjY1Ej4HIvU4vzIY_87827.pdf

Projects

AeROS

The project will deliver common virtualized services to enable orchestration, virtual communication (network-related programmable functions), and efficient support for frugal, explainable AI and creation of distributed data-driven applications. aerOS will be based on continuum infrastructure elements like smart devices, Tiny/far/near edge computing nodes, and public/private clouds (including virtual services and NetApps), providing scalable and secure access to applications and services while keeping its data autonomy. The solution will be generic and directly applicable to any vertical, cross-vertical business process, and several different physical or virtual platforms.

FluiDOS

This project will deliver a fluid, dynamic, scalable, and trustworthy computing continuum, spanning across devices and unifying edge and cloud in an energy-efficient manner. FluiDOS will build on consolidated operating systems and orchestration solutions, resource sharing in the computing continuum, AI-based optimization for cost and energy, and a zero-trust paradigm to enable an open, collaborative ecosystem that will support European digital autonomy. Stakeholders will be involved through pilots and demonstrators in the fields of agriculture, energy, and logistics, challenging the project's ability to adapt to different environments and operating conditions, showcasing its true innovation potential.

ICOS

This project will cover challenges of the IoT-edge-cloud paradigm, proposing an approach to embed a set of functionalities, defining an IoT-Cloud Operating System (ICOS). Its aim is to design, develop and validate a meta-operating system by addressing the challenges of device volatility and heterogeneity, continuum infrastructure virtualization and diverse network connectivity, optimized and scalable service execution and performance, as well as resources consumptions. It will also cover security, privacy, and trust, and reduce integration costs and effective mitigation of cloud provider lock-in effects, in a data-driven system built on openness, adaptability, data sharing and a future edge market scenario for services and data.

NebulOus

NebulOus will contribute to research in cloud and fog computing brokerage, by introducing advanced methods to enable secure and optimal application provisioning, resource adaptation and reconfiguration. It will contribute to the cloud computing continuum through the development of a meta-operating system and platform to exploit edge and fog nodes, in conjunction with multi-cloud resources, to cope with requirements posed by low latency applications.

NEMO

This project establishes itself as the gamechanger of the A IoT-edge-cloud continuum by introducing an open source, modular and cybersecure meta-operating system, leveraging on existing technologies and introducing novel concepts, methods, tools, testing and engagement campaigns. NEMO will bring intelligence closer to the data and make AI-as-a-Service an integral part of network self-organization and micro-services execution orchestration. Its widespread penetration and massive acceptance

will be achieved via new technology, pre-commercial exploitation components and liaison with open-source communities.

NEPHELE

This project's vision is to enable the efficient, reliable, and secure end-to-end orchestration of hyper-distributed applications over a programmable infrastructure spanning across the cloud-edge-IoT continuum, removing existing openness and interoperability barriers in the convergence of IoT technologies against cloud and edge computing orchestration platforms, and introducing automation and decentralized intelligence mechanisms powered by 5G and distributed AI technologies. The outcomes will be demonstrated, validated, and evaluated in a set of use cases across vertical industries such as energy, healthcare, and logistics.

Coordination actions

HiPEAC

HiPEAC will reinforce the development of Europe's computing ecosystem to support our digitalization by guiding the research and innovation (R&I) of key emerging technologies, sectors, and value chains. Its goal is to strengthen European leadership in the global data economy and accelerate the digital and green transitions through human-centred innovation. This will be achieved by mobilising partnerships and stakeholders to provide roadmaps on the creation of next-generation computing technologies, infrastructures, and platforms. The aim is to contribute to the technological development and market uptake of advanced applications across the value chain. This next generation of computing will increase European autonomy in the data economy, which is required to support future hyper-distributed applications and provide opportunities for the digital transformation of our economy and society, new business models, economic growth, and job creation.

OpenContinuum

OpenContinuum supports the cloud-edge-IoT domain by focusing on the supply side of the computing continuum landscape. Its goal is to foster European strategic autonomy and interoperability through an open ecosystem for the computing continuum, with open source and open standards as two key enablers to be supported and leveraged throughout the community. Such an ecosystem will contain R&I projects in the cloud-edge-IoT portfolio to be coordinated, the diverse community evolved from the current cloud and IoT ones, with the addition of actors, initiatives, and significant alliances. The supply-side nature of OpenContinuum's agenda will orient the themes and focus of project activities but will not limit the scope of community building. The project's active landscaping and engagement work will bring the cloud and IoT communities together and express all points of view with a common understanding. It will then provide guidance to European actors to contribute to and lead open-source projects and standardisation efforts.

Unlock-CEI

Unlock-CEI's ambition is to unlock the potential for accelerating the deployment of the cloud-edge-IoT (CEI) computing continuum in Europe by focusing on demand-side drivers and challenges to identify technology-driven innovation and business opportunities driving demand value chains. The project represents the cloud-edge-IoT

demand constituency, provides insights and guidance to Horizon Europe R&I projects, and contributes to a proactive dialogue with suppliers to encourage the development of an open European cloud-edge-IoT ecosystem. It focuses on emerging value chains where investment is needed to foster the deployment of the cloud-edge-IoT continuum through forthcoming large-scale pilots, which will ultimately foster European autonomy in the digital economy.

Other relevant EU founded projects

5G-VINNI

5G-VINNI¹⁰ project aims to accelerate the uptake of 5G in Europe by providing a highly advanced end-to-end facility to validate the performance of new 5G technologies. Researchers will test network visualization techniques and advanced network architectures such as 5G network slicing as a service.

5G-VINNI uses the ecosystem of services defined by 3GPP (see 3GPP TS 28.530) to offer its customers (5G-VINNI customer) the services provided by each provider (5G-VINNI facility)

5Growth

5Growth¹¹ is an AI-driven automated 5G E2E service platform that integrates 5G connectivity with network slicing, virtualization and multi-domain solutions. Custom network slices are instantiated to concurrently support the service requirements of multiple, heterogeneous applications over a shared network infrastructure that not only comprises different types of resources (e.g., at the edge, cloud, and transport) but also spans across multiple administrative domains (e.g., PNI-NPN scenario).

5G-CLARITY

5G-CLARITY¹² implements an SDN/NFV platform that is composed of a Management and Orchestration stratum and an Intelligence stratum.

A 5G-CLARITY slice is defined as an on-premise infrastructure slice, i.e., an isolated set of resources that are segregated from the private infrastructure for their delivery to separate tenants. This means 5G-CLARITY slicing enables isolation among tenants. Note that the use of network slicing in 5G-CLARITY differs from the one in 3GPP community, i.e., while for 5G-CLARITY it is multi-tenancy support, for 3GPP it is multi-service support (the ability to deliver tailored functionality for different services). Once a single 5G-CLARITY slice is delivered to a specific tenant, one or more customer-facing services could be provisioned using the set of resources (hereinafter referred as resource chunks) which comprises this 5G-CLARITY slice. These customer-facing services (augmented reality applications, enhance positioning automated guided vehicles) could be modelled as one or more ETSI-NFV network services, i.e., a composition of NFs implemented as VNFs and a set of wireless and transport services configured on PNFs, as they will be defined later. The delivered 5G-CLARITY slice

¹⁰ <https://www.5g-vinni.eu/>

¹¹ <https://5growth.eu/>

¹² <https://www.5gclarity.com/>

could be deployed across different network domains, i.e., RAN Transport Network (TN) or Core Network (CN). This means the 5G-CLARITY slice has an E2E nature.

Other open-source projects

Liqo

Liqo¹³ is an open-source project that enables dynamic and seamless Kubernetes multi-cluster topologies, supporting heterogeneous on-premise, cloud and edge infrastructures. Liqo provides the following capabilities:

Peering

Automatic peer-to-peer establishment of **resource and service consumption relationships** between independent and heterogeneous clusters. No need to worry about complex VPN configurations and certification authorities: everything is transparently **self-negotiated** for you.

Offloading

Seamless **workloads offloading** to remote clusters, without requiring any modification to Kubernetes or the applications themselves. **Multi-cluster is made native and transparent**: collapse an entire remote cluster to a **virtual node** compliant with the standard Kubernetes approaches and tools.

Network Fabric

A transparent **network fabric**, enabling multi-cluster **pod-to-pod** and **pod-to-service** connectivity, regardless of the underlying configurations and CNI plugins. Natively **access the services** exported by remote clusters, and spread interconnected application components across multiple infrastructures, with all cross-cluster traffic flowing through **secured network tunnels**.

Storage Fabric

A native **storage fabric**, supporting the remote execution of **stateful workloads** according to the **data gravity** approach. Seamlessly extend standard (e.g., database) **high availability deployment techniques** to the multi-cluster scenarios, for **increased guarantees**. All without the complexity of managing multiple independent cluster and application replicas.

EPOS Fog

EPOS Fog¹⁴ focus in service placement for the Internet of Things. EPOS Fog introduces a decentralized multi-agent system for collective learning that utilizes edge-to-cloud nodes to jointly balance the input workload across the network and minimize the costs involved in service execution. The agents locally generate possible assignments of requests to resources and then cooperatively select an assignment such that their combination maximizes edge utilization while minimizes service execution cost. Extensive experimental evaluation with realistic Google cluster workloads on various networks demonstrates the superior performance of EPOS Fog in terms of workload balance and QoS, compared to approaches such as First Fit and

¹³ <https://liqo.io/>

¹⁴ <https://github.com/epournaras/EPOS-Fog>

exclusively Cloud-based. The results confirm that EPOS Fog reduces service execution delay up to 25% and the load-balance of network nodes up to 90%. The findings also demonstrate how distributed computational resources on the edge can be utilized more cost-effectively by harvesting collective intelligence.

ioFog

ioFog¹⁵ try to resolve the problem of edge computing in volatile environments. ioFog is an edge computing platform for deploying, running, and networking distributed microservices at the edge.

ioFog aims to make developing edge software just like developing for the cloud. Distributed Internet of Things (IoT) applications let you put your code at the edge, bring legacy devices into the IoT, and keep data anywhere you want.

An Edge Compute Network (ECN) running ioFog is made up of one or more devices, referred to as nodes. Each node runs a daemon service called an Agent. Each node's Agent is a daemon that is responsible for one or more microservices running on that particular node. These microservices are deployed using Linux kernel containers (LXC). Most people use Docker, for its ease, stability, and vibrant community.

Since Edge Compute Networks are usually distributed—composed of many different devices across networks, each with potentially differing microservices—a piece of software called the Controller is used for orchestration of the different Agents.

Because the Controller daemon keeps track of all your Agents automatically, even across complicated network configurations, it can be used to maintain the entire fleet. Small Edge Compute Networks will only need a single Controller, which can be run on any device, including one that also happens to run the Agent too, as long as it has a stable hostname or static IP address and is reachable by all the Agents.

For microservices that need to communicate with other nodes in your network, ioFog includes an optional daemon called the Skupper AMQP Dispatch routers.

8.1.2 Innovations in 6GSMART-ICC

The industrial world has become completely dynamic with the arrival of the IIoT (Industrial IoT). There is an increasing number of devices with greater intelligence that allow more and more use cases to be automated. Managing this huge number of resources is not an easy task, much less when the components can become volatile, as is the case with drones, whose service time depends fundamentally on the capacity of the included battery.

In this project we are going to investigate what should be the best approach to minimize the time of unavailability of the services, knowing that normally the resources available on extreme edge and on-premises are usually quite scarce. In this sense, different deployment strategies will be evaluated, such as:

- Continuously monitor the status of the node and, if it is not available, deploy the components located in that node in another node that is available. In general,

¹⁵ <https://iofog.org/>

this is the behavior of Kubernetes, but in our case, the service replacement time may be too high.

- Duplicate each component instance on two separate nodes. The second instance will remain in passive mode until the node where the primary instance is running stops serving.
- Through Artificial Intelligence techniques, estimate the behavior of each resource and make predictions about the probable time in which they will stop providing the service, time in which the microservice would move to another node. It is outside of this project to make these predictions with artificial intelligence; however, the orchestrator will be prepared to receive said events from an external system.

In general, all the techniques that we use to improve the availability of services located in volatile resources will be improved by the fact of having a dynamic application virtual network that allows traffic to be directed to the appropriate instances at any time.

Another area of innovation also provided by application virtual networks is the dynamic control (autoscaling) of microservices from highly saturated compute zones to less saturated compute zones. The computing services offered by network operators will be distributed in different edges. Therefore, it makes sense to have an orchestrator with capabilities to move loads for situations in which congestion occurs at a certain edge, such as the case of an augmented reality application in a football match. In this case, to maintain an acceptable quality of service, more microservice instances could be created at another edge so that all the demand can be met as shown in Figure 6.

Figure 6 Edge offloading

These autoscaling capabilities could also be used to redistribute the loads within each datacenter so that in times of low activity (at night) the microservices are compacted into a few clusters (racks) and therefore the rest of the servers can be turned off to generate energetic savings. In this case, each datacenter should be organized in the form of small clusters that could be activated and deactivated from the orchestrator.

8.2 Intent mechanisms to integrate OT workloads into telco environments.

8.2.1 State of the art

There are some initiatives trying to harmonize the deployment of services and applications using resources from both the edge and the public cloud in telco environments. Some initiatives launched by operators, by standardization bodies (3GPP) and by the business world are described below.

Operators' initiative: Sylva

Deutsche Telekom, Orange, Telecom Italia, Telefonica and Vodafone got together to collaborate on the creation of a cloud software framework. Again, the stated aim was to reduce the infrastructure fragmentation, within the European context. This time, though, two vendors were also involved – Nokia and Ericsson.

The project, known as Sylva¹⁶, is homed within Linux Foundation Europe (LF Europe). Its members have two main aims. First, to “create a new, open-source production-grade Telco Cloud Stack” – i.e. a cloud software framework. Secondly, to produce a Reference Implementation of that framework.

Sylva's main objective is to release a cloud native infrastructure stack to host Telco (5G, OpenRAN, CDN, etc.) and Edge use cases. The main technical challenges that Sylva is targeting are Network performance, Distributed Cloud (multi cluster Kubernetes, Bare Metal Automation), Energy Efficiency, Security (hardening and compliance) and Openness (capitalise and contribute to Anuket, Nephio, O-RAN). A launch press release from the group said, “Sylva provides an environment to collaborate and develop solutions to tackle specific technology challenges and facilitate cloud native adaptation for Telco and Edge use cases”.

The aim of the cloud software framework is to:

- Identify and prioritize telco and edge requirements.

- Develop solutions to the specific technical challenges identified on the infrastructure layer of the telco ecosystem.

- Integrate these solutions with existing open-source components.

¹⁶ <https://gitlab.com/sylva-projects/sylva>

These solutions and the integrated cloud software framework are not “production ready” software, but aims to be “production grade” in order to be used by third parties such as operators, network function vendors, and cloud providers to create commercial products.

Why are they doing this?

Telcos know they will need to deploy hundreds of Edge Cloud nodes in the coming years, accommodating traditional telco functionality such as 5G Radio Access Network (RAN), core network, BGP, SDN functions and modern cloud services such as video analysis or control platforms for robotics in the same location. Cloud Native Infrastructure offers a great opportunity to make this deployment simple and efficient.

The white paper¹⁷ says that the problem they face is that, if the Telco industry continues with its traditional deployment model, then fragmentation is inevitable for the deployment of applications that mandate the use of proprietary CaaS (Container as a Service) and even specific physical compute as shown in Figure 7.

Source sylvia

Figure 7 Fragmentation from Vendor point of view

This paper says this approach is no longer sustainable as it:

- Prevents the possibility of sharing CaaS and physical resources among different applications, resulting in wasted compute power with CAPEX and energy impacts

- Creates unnecessary complexity for vendors as they look to certify multiple cloud platforms

- Creates operational burdens on Telcos as the different “islands” will need different skills and will evolve at different speeds

¹⁷ https://gitlab.com/sylvia-projects/sylvia/-/blob/main/White_Paper_Operators_Sylvia.pdf

Fails to provide a solution that can evolve with the necessary speed of cloud native

So what are the telcos looking for, from Sylva, that can overcome these issues?

The whitepaper says it wants to close gaps in the infrastructure technology to be able to support telco apps, but to do so in a common way. It says, “Although Kubernetes’ customizability... makes the technology great in utilizing any type of Compute Hardware, as a result of how the interfaces are designed the CaaS layers do not abstract the Compute Hardware completely from the Applications. There are some technology areas where Cloud Native infrastructure components need to evolve to support the needs of Telco applications. When closing the gaps in the infrastructure technology the most optimal approach for the whole industry is to develop open source de-facto standard interfaces instead of vendor specific solutions.”

Here is a list of some of these extended capabilities required by Sylva use cases:

Enhanced performance support (e.g.: EPA capabilities, DPDK, SRV-IO)

Specific synchronization cards support for O-RAN (PTP)

Cloud Native support for L1 RAN acceleration network interface cards

GPU hardware support

Bare Metal automation provisioning

Multi-Clustering support

Service mesh support

Enhanced security (e.g.: Internal ciphering and multi-tenancy)

Lightweight (all in 1 server)

Energy efficiency.

Having one consistent computing platform that can be deployed, sharing hardware and connectivity resources among different applications, can “reduce fragmentation of the cloud infrastructure layer for telecommunication and edge services”.

In a large part, Sylva is about providing that implementation platform for a distributed cloud that meets telco needs, evolving them away from relying on proprietary vendor clouds, operator clouds, public clouds etc.

Sylva said it is not intended to replace those other efforts but to leverage them and cover those requirements that are specific for the use cases that European Telcos are working on.

Project Sylva is not starting from scratch, though. It is using Anuket, which is an open initiative that delivers a common model, standardised reference infrastructure specifications, and conformance and performance frameworks for virtualised and cloud native network functions. However, Sylva says it is not a duplication of Anuket. Rather, “Sylva is a production-grade cloud framework implementation compliant with the reference architecture (RA2) and the conformance test suites (RC2) from Anuket.”

And Sylva is also aware that there are already other initiatives covering cloud native technology stacks such as Kubernetes and the Anuket itself, as well as other initiatives that cover specifying, integrating and verifying Telco-specific stacks and the validation of Telco applications.

If needed, the Sylva project will contribute to those initiatives some specific extensions that could otherwise become duplications.

Why not just leverage the public cloud?

Well, the telcos feel that while hyperscalers can provide to both operators and vendors the capabilities they need, this solution will remain a vertical solution with no interoperability between hyperscalers themselves, and strong lock in.

Another difference with this project is the explicit involvement of the two NF vendors. The vendors themselves are challenged by cloud and cloud infrastructure fragmentation as it means they have to develop software for a whole gamut of different telco cloud environments. Of course, the vendors also offer operators their own cloud environments, but when they are faced with deploying to a telco cloud, the question of who manages that, and takes charge of ongoing updates and deployment, is difficult for those vendors too.

These issues are only magnified in distributed use cases, where resource sharing and flexibility is more important than in a showcase centralised cloud environment that might host, say, a new 5G SA-capable core network.

Standardization groups: 3GPP intent

The current 5G networks bring more operational complexities, and the telecom system need to be able to adapt their operation to the business objectives of the operator as well as expectations of customer, which is driving customer to shift the focus from "how" to "what ". An intent driven system will be able to learn the behavior of networks and services and allows a customer to provide the desired state, without detailed knowledge of how to get to the desired state. Thus, intent driven management is introduced to reduce the complexity of management without getting into the intricate detail of the underlying network resources.

An intent specifies the expectations including requirements, goals and constraints for a specific service or network management workflow. The intent may provide information on particular objective and possibly some related details. Following are some general concepts for intent:

- An intent is typically understandable by humans, and also needs to be interpreted by the machine without any ambiguity.
- An intent focuses more on describing the "What" needs to be achieved but less on "How" that outcomes should be achieved, the intent expresses the metrics that need to be achieved and not how to achieve them. This not only relieves the burden of the consumer knowing implementation details but also leaves room to allow the producer to explore alternative options and find optimal solutions. Try to describe the properties that allows a satisfactory outcome.
- The expectations expressed by an intent is agnostic to the underlying system implementation, technology and infrastructure. Area can be used as managed

object in the expectations expressed by an intent to achieve system implementation, technology and infrastructure agnostic.

- An intent needs to be quantifiable from network data so that the fulfillment result can be measured and evaluated.

Intent can be categorized based on different user types or different management scenario types. Based on roles related to 5G networks and network slicing management defined in clause 12 in 3GPP TS 28.530, different kinds of intents are applicable for different kinds of standardized reference interfaces as shown in Figure 8.

Figure 8 3GPP Intent kinds

Intent from Communication Service Customer (Intent-CSC): Intent from Communication Service Customer enables Communication Service Customer (CSC) to express which properties of a communication service the CSC may request from CSP without knowing how to do the detailed management for communication service. For example, Intent-CSC can be 'Enable a V2X communication service for a group of vehicles at certain time'.

Intent from Communication Service Provider (Intent-CSP): Intent from Communication Service Provider enables Communication Service Provider (CSP) to express an intent about what CSP would like to do for network without knowing how to do the detailed management for network. For example, Intent-CSP can be 'Provide a network service supporting V2X communications for highway-417 to support 500 vehicles simultaneously'.

Intent from Network Operator (Intent-NOP): Intent from Network Operator enables Network Operator (NOP) to provide what NOP would like to do for group of network elements (i.e., subnetwork) management and control without knowing how to do the detailed management for the network elements. For example, Intent-NOP can be 'Provide a radio network service to satisfy the specified coverage requirements and UE throughput requirement in certain area'.

Commercial solutions: ori

Ori Global Cloud¹⁸ (OGC) is a powerful application orchestration platform designed to simplify and automate the deployment and management of cloud-based applications. With OGC, users can easily configure and deploy complex applications across multiple cloud environments, including public and private clouds.

Simplified and secure networking

Ori's Global Cloud makes policy-driven routing and networking at the application level a breeze. Instantly connect every component seamlessly and securely, no matter which cloud, cluster, or environment they call home as shown in Figure 9.

Source ori.co

Figure 9 ORI global cloud

The Ori Global Cloud (OGC) application orchestration platform is built on several core concepts, including:

- **Infrastructure Clusters:** OGC allows users to onboard and manage Kubernetes clusters within the platform, providing a centralized location to manage and deploy their applications and services.
- **Projects:** Users can create and manage projects within the platform, allowing them to organize and manage their applications and services.

¹⁸ <https://ori.co/platform>

- **Packages:** Users can package their applications as self-contained, portable units, making it easy to deploy and orchestrate them across different cloud environments.
- **Deployments:** Users can deploy their packaged applications on Kubernetes clusters across different cloud environments, including popular platforms such as AWS, Azure, and Google Cloud.

Overall, these core concepts of infrastructure clusters, projects, packages, and deployments provide a framework for users to manage and automate their cloud-based applications and services using the OGC platform. By leveraging these core concepts, users can easily manage and deploy their applications and services in a scalable and efficient manner, reducing complexity and improving overall productivity.

8.2.2 Innovations in 6GSMART-ICC

Intent deployment model

In this project, a novel approach will be evaluated to optimally locate the components that are part of each application in the set of computing resources (extreme edge, on-premises and telco edge) that the orchestrator has available. In this model, the orchestrator decides in which resource/cloud each microservice should be located based on a modeling of resources and applications that is described below.

A model of interconnected resources is defined that allows to identify at all times the possible locations of the different components that are part of the application. The model labels and characterizes all the resources so that the load location algorithms are as efficient as possible.

The resources are labeled with the type of resource (extreme edge, on-premises and telco edge), with the volatility capacity (volatile, non-volatile) and with labels defined by the end user in order to allow the definition of placement rules. Likewise, each resource will be characterized with its capacity (CPU, Memory, Disk, GPU, SR-IOV, etc.) as well as with other particular characteristics that are relevant when locating loads, such as latency and bandwidth, both with respect to the end user and between resources. Finally, the resources are linked between them by means of links in order to establish the network connectivity according to which the different components can communicate internally.

Once the resource model is defined, the application model needs to be defined. A distributed application is defined as a set of microservices that communicate with each other and with the end user to provide a specific service. For reasons of high availability or performance, many of the microservices usually require multiple instances to be deployed. The resources that the orchestrator works with are Kubernetes clusters. Kubernetes has different deployment models that allow you to deploy multiple instances of each component. This project goes further and establishes multi-cluster models so that microservices can not only be distributed within Kubernetes clusters but also extend to different Kubernetes clusters

The application model includes a cost model and a component connectivity model.

The component connectivity model allows filtering based on the rest of the components deployed in the application. Each component can have connectivity with the end user and/or with other components that act as servers for said component. With this model,

the possible location of the component will be refined to those resources (clouds) that have the necessary connectivity with the rest of the already deployed components of the application.

Finally, the cost model allows more data to be included in the resource/cloud selection model where to locate the application component. The cost model takes into account parameters such as the latency of the resource from the user and with other resources, the bandwidth from the user and with other resources, etc. The model will filter all those clouds that do not allow the location of the load, for example because the latency with the user is too high, and will generate a cost function based the remaining capacity in them.

Virtual Application Networks

This project will also explore the operation of virtual application networks that allow the different microservices that are part of an application to be easily connected so that they do not have to know in which resource each component is running. To implement virtual application networks, we will use **Skupper**¹⁹.

A Virtual Application Network (VAN) connects the applications and services in your hybrid cloud into a virtual network so that they can communicate with each other as if they were all running in the same site. In Figure 10, a VAN connects three services, each of which is running in a different cloud:

Source skupper

Figure 10 Clouds overview

In essence, the VAN connects the services in a distributed application with a microservice architecture as show in Figure 11.

¹⁹ <https://skupper.io/>

Figure 11 Application overview

VANs are able to provide connectivity across the hybrid cloud because they operate at Layer 7 (the application layer). They use Layer 7 application routers to route communication between Layer 7 application addresses.

Layer 7 application routers

Layer 7 application routers form the backbone of a VAN in the same way that conventional network routers form the backbone of a VPN. However, instead of routing IP packets between network endpoints, Layer 7 application routers route messages between application endpoints (called Layer 7 application addresses).

Layer 7 application addresses

A Layer 7 application address represents an endpoint, or destination in the VAN. When an application sends a communication to an address, the Layer 7 application routers distribute the communication to any other application in the VAN that has the same address.

For example, in Figure 12, Service B sends a message with an application address to its local application router. Service A and Service C are subscribed to the same address, so the application router routes copies of the message through the VAN until they arrive at each destination.

Source skupper

Figure 12 Routes overview

VANs provide multiple routing patterns, so communications can be distributed in anycast (balanced or closest) or multicast patterns.

Skupper

Skupper is an open source tool for creating VANs in Kubernetes. By using Skupper, you can create a distributed application consisting of microservices running in different Kubernetes clusters.

Figure 13 illustrates a Skupper network that connects three services running in three different Kubernetes clusters:

Source skupper

Figure 13 Cluster overview

In a Skupper network, each namespace contains a Skupper instance. When these Skupper instances connect, they continually share information about the services that each instance exposes. This means that each Skupper instance is always aware of

every service that has been exposed to the Skupper network, regardless of the namespace in which each service resides.

Once a Skupper network is formed across Kubernetes namespaces, any of the services in those namespaces can be exposed (through annotation) to the Skupper network. When a service is exposed, Skupper creates proxy endpoints to make that service available on each namespace in the Skupper network.

9 Initial architecture design for a industry 4.0 Meta-OS

9.1 System requirements

The main requirements that the system must meet are described below:

Resource Life-Cycle Control. To be able to have a complete control over virtual resources. The solution needs to control life-cycle of each virtual resource and its different states such as power on, power off, etc.

Service/Application Life-Cycle Control. To be able to have a complete control over the services/applications deployed in virtual resources. The solution needs to control life-cycle of each service, including start, stop, configure, reconfigure, deploy, and redeploy services/applications.

Multitenancy Support. This refers to the mode of operation of the solution where resources are isolated to allow the sharing of them across multiple network operators (tenants). The services of each tenant are logically isolated over the same physical infrastructure. In 5G, for example, multiple network operators (tenants) can share the same physical infrastructure whilst operating independently logically.

Multizone Support. This is the capability to enable distributed deployment of services across multiple zones and to deploy services faster than in a centralized architecture by making use of data locality to speed up deployments.

Service/Application Location Awareness. This is the capability to use the geographical position to define zones within the infrastructure. The solution should be able to deploy services/applications in a specific location. This feature provides to the infrastructure administrator the functionality to deploy services in each zone and ensures that architecturally it is the best solution for the user.

Parallel Deployment. This is the capability of the solution to support parallel deployment and to deploy new services or applications. These activities may include virtual procurements, configuration, tuning, staging, installation, and interoperability testing.

Performance Monitoring. This is the capability of the solution to obtain performance metrics of the used resources in order to get possible problems and optimize the use of the available resources.

High available. This refers to the mode of operation trying to reduce the possible downtime of the solution. Normally high availability systems have redundant components and apply fault-tolerant rules.

Resilient. Resiliency seeks to guarantee recovery and adaptation capacity, minimizing negative impacts and protecting the systems and people involved.

Secure. The solution must be designed with security at its core to span the boundaries of applications, clouds and users. It must encrypt data at rest and in motion with authentication and authorization features that secure the orchestrator and the clouds to which it connects.

Scalable. The solution must have an architecture that is simple enough for a single application in a single cloud, but that can scale to meet the need of the world's largest cloud service providers, which have many isolated tenants, each with multiple a

Backup & disaster recovery. It should be possible to configure a backup strategy to preserve all necessary data for complete restore of all components in the solution.

9.2 High-Level System Design

The solution proposed is a cloud continuum management platform that securely deploys application components on extreme edge, on-premises and telco edge environments.

The resources to be deployed are modeled as applications, which in turn are modeled as sets of components linked according to a mesh. The solution is multi-tenant, which allows each tenant to define their set of clouds where the components of their applications can be deployed. For this, the access accounts to each cloud must be provided by each tenant.

The solution uses a new intent model that allows the orchestrator to decide at any time which is the best location (best cloud/resource) where each component of each application instance should reside. The cloud selection algorithm is based on the following capabilities mainly: Deployment Models, Component Connectivity and Cost Model.

This project goes further and establishes multi-cluster models so that microservices can not only be distributed within Kubernetes clusters but also extend to different Kubernetes clusters. The orchestrator supports different Kubernetes-style **deployment models** that specify the requirements of the components that must be deployed. The following deployment models are supported:

N-Unrestricted: It is a model in which the creation of N instances of a component is requested in any of the clouds available to the tenant.

PerCloudType: It is a model in which the creation of 1 component instance is requested in all clouds of a certain type.

PerCloudLabel: It is a model in which the creation of 1 component instance is requested in all the clouds that have a certain label.

N-ToCloudLabel: This is a model that requests the creation of N component instances located in clouds that have a certain label.

Figure 14 shows possible component locations according to the models described above:

■ Per cloud type
 ■ N-Unrestricted
 ■ Per cloud label
 ■ N-To cloud label

Figure 14 Deployment models

The **component connectivity model** makes it possible to define the connectivity relationships between the different components of an application, said relationships being directional. In other words, each component has an impact on what other components it needs to communicate with, acting as a client of a service. This functionality allows filtering of selectable clouds for each component instance, taking into account the location selection that has been previously made for other components. The cloud selection algorithm for each component will start with components that have direct user interface and continue with components that expose services for other components. On the other hand, not all clouds will be connected to each other. For two clouds to be connected, a Virtual Network Application (VAN) needs to be established so that the components of both clouds can communicate. This part of the algorithm allows filtering clouds that do not have the necessary connectivity to instantiate each specific component.

Finally, the **cost model** allows a refinement on the selectable clouds to date. This model takes into account the particular characteristics of each cloud (remaining capacity, latency to the user, etc.) and the characteristics of the links between clouds (latency between clouds, bandwidth) and based on this it filters those clouds that do not comply with the requirements of that component.

If after applying the deployment model there are several selectable clouds, then the one whose remaining capacity function is greater will be selected. The capacity function will be defined as a function that will take as inputs both initial and used CPU, memory, and disk in a cloud and will return a level of combined capacity remaining.

It can happen that there are components for which the selected model is not allowed to be deployed (for example in the case of PerCloudType when a cloud of that type no longer has capacity). To take this case into account, it may be indicated in the definition of the components whether the application of the model must be fully complied with or whether a best effort type deployment is supported. In any case, if the orchestrator is not able to carry out the deployment fully complying with the requirements, it will notify the end user.

Architecture

Figure 15 shows the proposed architecture for the orchestrator.

Figure 15 Orchestrator Architecture

The orchestrator is based on the following components:

Controllers

Controllers are responsible for managing the entire life cycle of the resource they are controlling. The used controllers are:

Account controller

Allows you to manage the different users that make use of the orchestrator grouped in tenant. It will manage both the access credentials of the users as well as the different functionalities of the application to which each user has access.

Cloud controller

It allows each tenant to manage the different clouds on which to deploy their application components. Among the data that is needed to register a cloud, this are the principal characteristics included in the model:

- Tenant credentials to manage cloud resources.

- Cloud capacity.

- Latency and available bandwidth of the user of the services to said cloud.

- Connectivity with other clouds.

- Cloud type: static or volatile.

The controller will monitor the state of the cloud at all times (particularly volatile clouds) and will apply a possible migration of components to another cloud if deemed necessary.

The management of the connectivity between clouds is delegated to the Virtual Application Manager, which is based on Skupper and allows establishing links between the different clouds.

Application controller

Allows the design of applications and their components. Each application is defined as a set of components that are either accessed by the end user or are accessed from other components.

For each component, the deployment model will be indicated, as well as the connectivity network and the cost model. For example, in the cost model, things such as that the latency with the end user does not exceed a certain value or that the latency with a service that must be accessed as a client must not exceed a certain threshold, will be indicated. Of course, each component will indicate the capacity requirements (CPU, Memory, Disk, etc.) necessary.

Components may also have temporal requirements that indicate whether component instances support a temporal execution model so that depending on the time of day the application virtual network directs traffic to a particular cloud.

App Instance controller

The application instance controller is responsible for managing the life cycle of application instances. To do this, it is responsible for choosing the cloud in which each component instance has to be deployed and ensuring that components deployed in volatile clouds continue to run. To determine the cloud in which to deploy each component instance, use the Intent Scheduler. To manage the life cycle of each component instance in each cloud, use Cloud Manager. In the event that it is detected that a certain component has stopped because a volatile cloud has ceased to be active, the most convenient actions will be carried out, which may result in the deployment of that component instance in another cloud.

Artifact controller

This controller is closely related to the Application controller and is in charge of uploading to the repository the necessary artifacts to deploy the component instances. Only the management of Helm chart repositories is provided, leaving the management of container images outside the scope of this solution.

Managers

Managers are responsible for providing the necessary capabilities to interact with external systems (clouds and repositories). The managers used are:

Cloud Manager

Allows deployments on different clouds (extreme edge, on-premises, edge). In addition to carrying out the deployments, it will allow you to know the status of each managed cloud and the components deployed in said cloud.

Virtual Application Network Manager

It allows linking the different clouds with a virtual application network and exposing the services offered by the component instances so that they can be used by other components.

Artifact Manager

Allows to register in the Helm Charts repository the artifacts used by the application components.

Intent Scheduler

The intent scheduler is responsible for selecting the cloud in which each component instance will be located. It is the most complex component that applies the rules of deployment models, many connections between components and cost model.

Databases

For the databases we use MongoDB, which is a JSON document-oriented database that fits perfectly into the philosophy of the project. A database will be defined for each type of managed resource: Accounts, Clouds, Applications, Application Instances and Artifacts.

NBI

All the functionalities will be exposed by an NBI that can be used either through a web interface, a command line or directly programmatically through the exposed OpenAPI.

10 Summary and conclusions

Numerous efforts are being made in the telecommunications and cloud ecosystems to respond to the challenges of continuum cloud computing. Both public cloud providers and orchestration solution providers for telecommunications operators are making significant efforts to respond to the deployment of applications at the edge. At this moment we find ourselves in a very fragmented landscape with open-source solutions (OSM, ONAP), public cloud solutions (AWS, GDC, Azure), private IT NFV providers

(VMware, RedHat, Netcraker, NearByOne) and solutions from traditional vendors (Nokia, Ericsson).

Current solutions do not provide an adequate response to the new challenges of continuous cloud such as partition tolerance in distributed applications, lack of automated mesh network/communication features, volatile resource management, telco cloud solutions not replicable in on-prem environments.

At 6GSMART-ICC we are going to study some of the above challenges to identify the reference designs that should be followed in the development of the continuous cloud orchestrator. Specifically, we are going to work on:

- Modeling and management of volatile resources. It is about minimizing the unavailability time of a given application component due to the characteristics of volatile resources.
- Deployment model based on intent. The orchestrator maintains full control over the clouds that should be used to deploy the application components.
- Virtual application networks that make distributed application programming a reality. Through these networks, various autoscaling mechanisms will be studied.